

Analysis of tour reviews using Sentiment Analysis

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Abstract—In the modern world, technology has a big impact on travel and tourism. Sentiment analysis is viewed as a classification task because it divides a text's orientation into positive and negative categories. To assess feedback and survey responses, online and social media content, and healthcare materials, sentiment analysis is commonly used in marketing, customer service, clinical medicine, and other areas. This article presents experimental results using Support Vector Machine (SVM) on benchmark datasets to build a sentiment classifier. When you read customer reviews, you can see right away if a tourist is satisfied or dissatisfied.

Keywords—sentiment analysis, Support Vector Machine, Colab, Linear Regression, CountVectorizer

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the fascinating and constantly developing fields is tourism. Thanks to modern technology, it is now even more fascinating. Tourism presents itself as an industry that is closely linked to a variety of international industries and sectors, ranging from business to the preservation of cultural heritage and environmental protection. When it comes to a nation's infrastructure and economy, tourism has positive consequences and advantages that foster growth. This study attempts to make it easier for the owner of Edge Around to categorise positive and negative opinions using sentiment analysis techniques.

Finding authors' thoughts about particular items is the goal of sentiment analysis, also known as opinion mining. Sentiment analysis in reviews is the technique of examining online product reviews to ascertain the general consensus. Sentiment analysis is viewed as a classification task because it divides a text's orientation into positive and negative categories. The classification method has been carried out using Support Vector Machines (SVM). They are a collection of supervised learning methods for outlier detection, classification, and regression. The advantages of support vector machines include: efficient in areas with great dimensions. Still helpful in circumstances where there are more dimensions than there are samples. The method for review analysis are:

- Text pre-processing: Users examine the text and eliminate stop words.
- Sentiment generation: It is based on user evaluations of a specific package.
- Support vector machines: An approach for supervised machine learning that is utilised for both regression and classification

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The use of non-English languages for sentiment analysis is one of the main issues with natural language processing, according to the research [1]. In this paper, we describe a simple but efficient algorithm that delivers precise results when immediately assessing the sentiment of the comments in non-English languages.

Through comments and evaluations, the work generates a large amount of unstructured data points [2]. Unfortunately, unstructured data analytics are more challenging. Examining and locating the emotions that underlie other people's perspectives on various subjects is the aim of sentiment analysis.

One of the core issues with sentiment analysis, sentiment polarity categorization, is what we plan to address in this paper[3]. With thorough process descriptions, a general procedure for sentiment polarity categorization is suggested. In their study [4], they looked at sentiment analysis of twitter data. Regarding domains, [5] revisited the area of sentiment analysis using a collection of machine learning-based approaches for categorizing news articles on cricket and sports.

User-generated content (UGC), which includes everything from blogs and social media posts to online travel review sites, is one of the most significant data sources for big data. UGC consists of thoughtful comments made impulsively by people. This evaluation data is generally accessible for little to no cost and can also be acquired with ease [6]. Such feedback may also have financial significance in areas like brand communication, customer-company relationships, and targeted advertising .

III. METHODOLOGY

The goal of this study is to develop a machine learning model that can accurately determine whether a user's review is favorable or negative using the provided dataset. The training and testing data sets are created from the dataset. For the model to learn accurately, more data should be used during training. This model's output can be used to produce review categorization. To identify positive and negative sentiment, the Support Vector Machine and SkLearn will be utilized. The structure is:

Figure 1:Review analysis methodology

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Information Gathering
2. Data Preprocessing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing
5. Result

A. Information Gathering: The properties of the dataset of customer reviews from different websites are utilised to train the model. The dataset has two columns and more than 20,000 rows. Reviews and ratings are in the columns. The kaggle website provided the dataset.

B. Data Pre-processing: Data reduction, data transformation, and data cleaning are all part of this process. All of this is done to increase the data's effectiveness. To improve the accuracy of our model, the data can be processed. In order for the categorisation to be accurate.

- **Cleaning Data:** First, the data is cleansed. This is where users are eliminating incomplete or undesired entries, such as empty cells. The dataset

can also be cleared of the noisy data. All the duplicates are eliminated in here.

- **Removing Stop Words:** The datasets are cleared of the stop words. These are the ones that appear the most frequently yet aren't given much weight in the text. This can be done to increase the model's accuracy.
- **Assigning Sentiment:** The sentiments are assigned to the review according to the corresponding ratings\
- **Splitting of data:** The data is first cleaned, and then it is divided into training and testing datasets.

C. Machine Learning: In Google Colab, the algorithm has been fully implemented. The offered reviews are analysed using machine learning methods. To analyse this, various classifiers are available. The accuracy of the classifier depends on how it was trained. High accuracy should be required of classifiers. The techniques employed are:

- **Google Colab:** Colaboratory, is a tool by Google that helps us to run python code. It's mostly used to do machine learning
- **CountVectorizer:** It can be used to turn text into a vector based on how many words are in the text. As a result, the words will appear as a matrix. The frequency of each word appearing in the text is shown in each cell.
- **Support Vector Machine:** A relatively new method for predictors, both in classification and regression, is the Support Vector Machine (SVM). The Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a collection of supervised learning techniques for regression classification and analysis that analyses data and spots patterns. It is a technique for categorising both linear and nonlinear data. If the data can be separated linearly, the SVM looks for the linear kernel, a decision boundary that distinguishes between data from one class and another.

Figure 2:Support Vector Machine

The Python Libraries are as follows:

- **NumPy:** It is a library for the Python programming language, supports large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, as well as a large variety of high-

level mathematical operations that may be done on these arrays.

- Pandas: Pandas is a software suite for data analysis and manipulation designed for the Python programming language. It comprises data structures and processes for interacting with time series and mathematical tables.
- Sklearn: Scikit-learn is unquestionably the most useful Python library for machine learning. Sklearn includes a number of useful algorithms for machine learning and statistical modelling, including as classification, regression, clustering, and dimensionality reduction.

IV. BUILD MODEL

The primary stage is creating the model. The algorithms are used by the user when developing the model. The involved actions are:

1. Import all the necessary packages:

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from sklearn import svm
from sklearn.metrics import f1_score
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import CountVectorizer
```

2. Get the form of the data after adding it to a Data Frame.

```
[2] df=pd.read_csv("tripadvisor_hotel_reviews.csv")
df.head()
```

	Review	Rating
0	nice hotel expensive parking got good deal sta...	4
1	ok nothing special charge diamond member hitlo...	2
2	nice rooms not 4* experience hotel monaco seaf...	3
3	unique, great stay, wonderful time hotel monac...	5
4	great stay great stay, went seahawk game aweso...	5

3. The dataset should then be divided into training and testing datasets.

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
x_train,x_test,y_train,y_test=train_test_split(df_all.Review,df_all.Sentiment)

from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import CountVectorizer
v=CountVectorizer()
x_train_vec=v.fit_transform(x_train)
x_test_vec=v.transform(x_test)
```

4. Use the svm to classify the dataset and then find the accuracy

```
[11] from sklearn import svm
clf_svm=svm.SVC(kernel="linear")
clf_svm.fit(x_train_vec,y_train)

SVC(kernel='linear')

clf_svm.score(x_test_vec,y_test)

0.9647864362569286

[14] from sklearn.metrics import f1_score
f1_score(y_test,clf_svm.predict(x_test_vec),average=None)

array([0.91358513, 0.97598933])
```

V. RESULT

Sentiment analysis is the process of categorising writings according to the emotions they express. The three main processes of a typical sentiment analysis model are data preparation, review analysis, and sentiment classification. This article focuses on those three steps and covers representative techniques used in each. The outcome demonstrates that based on the provided dataset, the given reviews may be categorised as either positive or negative. The Passive Aggressive offers accurate results with a high level of 96% precision.

```
[ ] rev=["the whole package is not so great"]
rev_vec=v.transform(rev)
clf_svm.predict(rev_vec)

array(['Negative'], dtype=object)
```

```
[ ] rev=["the whole package is great"]
rev_vec=v.transform(rev)
clf_svm.predict(rev_vec)

array(['Positive'], dtype=object)
```

VI. CONCLUSION

This article outlines a process for analyzing the comments made by users of our packages. Natural language processing is used to perform sentimental analysis in the suggested model. Additionally, the system offers consumers who submit reviews of the service anonymity. In this case, the user put a solution into practice by first processing the data and then using countVectorizer to represent the data as a matrix. The Support Vector Machine was then utilized by the user to create a model to categories the reviews. It is hoped that a subsequent study would go even farther and develop a mobile software that can analyze text data quickly and effectively in any language and make it available for download on the Apple and Android platforms.

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